

Structured Exploratory Strategies in Volumetric Haptic Palpation of Virtual Phantom Tissues with Nodules Revealed by Trajectory-Based AI Inference

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Abstract. Digitalizing manual tissue examination requires also capturing the tactile expertise of human palpation. We present a haptic framework for studying and modeling exploratory strategies during volumetric tissue interaction, using an ex vivo-inspired virtual environment with uncertainty driven by coupled nodule size and depth. From pilot haptic trajectory data collected during nodule search tasks, LSTM models identify Global Scanning and Local Refinement behaviors and their transitions. Localized probing precedes improved detection-weighted localization, highlighting a trade-off between exploration and precision. These findings reveal structured exploratory strategies in haptic palpation and support encoding tactile expertise for haptic training systems and autonomous robotic palpation.

Keywords: Exploratory Haptics, Volumetric Palpation, Tactile Expertise Modeling,

1 Haptic exploration of virtual nodules: objectives and methods

In haptic perception and medical examination, palpation is a core process humans use to understand objects' mechanical properties, where hand movements and force modulation gradually reduce perceptual uncertainty [1-4]. A medical example is manual ex vivo tissue assessment, where pathologists' tactile expertise and detection performance refine over time. Most haptic research has focused on force-rendering quality and palpation outcomes [5-8]. While essential, these give limited insight into how information is gathered and used. Prior work has used temporal models for surface-based clinical exams [9,10], yet exploratory strategies during volumetric palpation remain difficult to quantify, especially when key discriminant information lies beneath the surface and must be actively uncovered. Recent works show that recurrent neural networks can predict human actions, uncover latent decision-making and distinguish behavioral strategies [11,12].

Participants interacted with a virtual bio-inspired phantom via Phantom Touch device (3D Systems) and a visual interface that showed geometry without revealing internal structure. Each phantom contained discrete spherical nodules embedded in a uniform square or circular substrate (Fig.2a). All nodules were positioned such that their centers lie at a constant depth so that larger nodules were contacted earlier during palpation, linking size and depth and preventing inference of nodule size, or relevance, from surface-level contact alone (Fig.2b). Stiffness could vary based on a linear and depth-dependent sigmoid profile, ensuring force magnitude alone was insufficient to reliably detect nodules (Fig.2c-d). The system operates as a multi-rate closed loop architecture (1 kHz haptic rendering, 30 Hz graphics, 50 Hz data collection) to capture temporal

A pilot study had participants detect and mark nodules in different phantom configurations, without knowing the underlying parameters, except for the visible phantom shape. To evaluate different parameter configurations, we computed the detection accuracy to measure the proportion of marked positions that successfully detected a nodule, the detection rate to measure the proportion of unique nodules correctly identified at least once per trial, the localization error to measure spatial precisions and dwell time to captures the proportion of time spent on a nodule. From haptic trajectories, we extracted time-aligned kinematic and force features and used them to train a Long-Short-Term-Memory (LSTM) neural network to classify interaction phases. Trajectories were segmented into fixed-duration temporal windows labeled as “Global Search” or “Local Refinement” based on contact with nodules, enabling analysis of how exploratory behaviors differ between scanning and localized refinement phases.

2 Emerging haptic exploration patterns: results and discussion

Participants exhibited a structured progression in their interaction with the virtual phantoms, progressing from early broad spatial coverage to increasingly localized motions around suspect regions. This transition was coupled with systematic changes in kinematic and force-related data, e.g. reduced distance from nodules and velocity (Fig.3a). Across participants, detection accuracy and dwell time (Mann-Whitney U, $p=0.03$) increased, detection rate improved (M-W U, $p=4.7 \times 10^{-15}$) and localization error decreased (M-W U, $p=6.6 \times 10^{-5}$), independently of trial configuration (Fig.3b). The LSTM-based model inferred distinct exploratory phases from haptic trajectories without access to nodule locations or task outcomes (Fig.3c). Segments classified as Global Search corresponded to wide motion patterns, while segments classified as Local Refinement corresponded to focused movements on nodules. These inferred phases aligned with the observed behavioral evolution, supporting the view of palpation as a temporally structured process, through which perceptual uncertainty is progressively resolved, rather than as a purely outcome-driven task [12]. Methodologically, the LSTM is used not as a predictive endpoint but as an analytical tool to reveal temporally structured patterns of exploratory behavior,

capturing transitions between search and refinement phases. From a haptics and perception standpoint, these findings indicate that users' exploration patterns over time offer complementary insights beyond traditional task outcomes. This can both inform haptic system evaluations and guide future paradigms for effective palpation exploration.

Fig.3. Emerging exploratory strategies (a) with dwell time over trials (b). Inference of exploratory intent from trajectories (c).

3 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange

The combination of task design, inducing active tactile exploration strategies, and LSTM-based analysis of haptic trajectories, emphasize how palpation behavior is intrinsically structured into temporally organized phases. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of exploratory haptics and provide a methodological basis for analyzing how tactile information is gathered over time during volumetric palpation tasks under uncertainty. Furthermore, we are actively seeking collaborators with expertise in clinical palpation, haptic interface design, and human perception or cognitive science, to further develop and validate this framework.

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Disclosure of Interests. CMO is co-inventor of patents related to haptic systems for medical applications.

References

1. Klatzky, Roberta L. "Haptic perception and its relation to action." *Annual review of psychology* 76.1 (2025): 227-250.,
2. Biswas, Shantonu, and Yon Visell. "Haptic perception, mechanics, and material technologies for virtual reality." *Advanced Functional Materials* 31.39 (2021): 2008186. Author, F.: Article title. *Journal* 2(5), 99–110 (2016)
3. Chan, Angela, et al. "Characterization of medical neck palpation to inform design of haptic palpation sensors." *Sensors* 25.7 (2025): 2159.
4. Xiao, Bo, et al. "Depth estimation of hard nodules in soft tissue by autonomous robotic palpation using deep recurrent neural network." *IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering* 17.4 (2020): 1791-1799.,
5. Profili, Alessandro, et al. "Telepalpation System for Stiffness Recognition of Tissue Digital Twins through Neuromorphic Vibrotactile Feedback in Virtual Reality." *2025 IEEE International Conference on Metrology for eXtended Reality, Artificial Intelligence and Neural Engineering (MetroXRINE)*. IEEE, 2025.
6. Abiri, Ahmad, et al. "Artificial palpation in robotic surgery using haptic feedback." *Surgical endoscopy* 33.4 (2019): 1252-1259.
7. Yu, Pijuan, et al. "Investigating passive presentation paradigms to approximate active haptic palpation." *IEEE Transactions on Haptics* 18.1 (2024): 208-219.
8. Lezkan, Alexandra, Anna Metzger, and Knut Drewing. "Active haptic exploration of softness: Indentation force is systematically related to prediction, sensation and motivation." *Frontiers in integrative neuroscience* 12 (2018): 59.
9. D'Abbraccio, Jessica, et al. "Haptic glove and platform with gestural control for neuromorphic tactile sensory feedback in medical telepresence." *Sensors* 19.3 (2019): 641.
10. Laufer, S., Pugh, C. M., & Van Veen, B. D. (2017). Modeling touch and palpation using autoregressive models. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 65(7), 1585-1594.
11. Laufer, Shlomi, Roberta L. Klatzky, and Carla M. Pugh. "Sensor-Based Discovery of Search and Palpation Modes in the Clinical Breast Examination." *Academic Medicine* 99. Supplement_1 (2024): S89-S94.
12. Auletta, Fabrizia, et al. "Predicting and understanding human action decisions during skillful joint-action using supervised machine learning and explainable-AI." *Scientific Reports* 13.1 (2023): 4992.